

THEORETICAL VIEWS ON THE LEXICAL AND GRAMMATICAL INTERPRETATION OF SOUND VERBS

Alijonova D.F.

2-course doctoral student of Namangan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14029819>

Abstract. *The given paper presents information regarding verb semantics and their features in world and Uzbek linguistics, which is based on these researches, the theoretical foundations of development of sound verbs in Uzbek language, where are voice verbs were explained in detail and clarified with examples.*

Keywords: *verb semantics, issues of lexical-semantic grouping of verbs, sound and verb concepts, sound verbs and their characteristics.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that despite of the fact that there are many and excellent studies on the verb group have been created in world linguistics, the semantic classification of verbs and the lexical-semantic description of these groups, their different aspects, denotative and connotative meanings, stylistic and the study of issues such as lexicographical explanation on the basis of modern linguistic achievements and paradigms has become an urgent task of the time.

Definitely, in Russian linguistics there are studies by G. Bagirov, S.A. Rzayev, Z. Budagova and L.M. Vasiliev. In particular, in L.M. Vasiliev's doctoral work, verbs are semantically divided into four types: verbs of perception, verbs of mental activity, verbs of speech, and verbs of behavior. This classification served as the basis for the original and subsequent studies.

Besides that, Russian linguists also carried out research on verb semantics in Turkish linguistics. For example, in the monographic works of N.K. Dmitriyev, verbs in Turkic languages were divided into four semantic groups: speech verbs, sense verbs, action verbs, action verbs. Professor Z. Budagova analyzed the verbs in the Azerbaijani language into 5 semantic groups: speech verbs, sense verbs, action verbs, action verbs, state verbs. L.N. Kharitonova researched verbs in Yakut language by dividing them into 3 semantic groups: verbs of action and state, verbs imitating sound, verbs imitating images, etc., these studies served as a foundation for Uzbek linguistics to reach a new level.

Main part. It should be admitted that in Uzbek linguistics, the verb-word group is considered a thoroughly researched area and has been studied in depth by such famous linguists as R. Rasulov, N. Makhmudov, A. Gulomov. In addition, there are studies devoted to semantic groups, structure, formation and valency of a group of verb words: A. Khodjiyev, I. Kochkortoyev "Semantics of speech verbs in Uzbek language", R. Rasulov "Case verbs in Uzbek language and their obligatory valencies ", T. Musaev on semantic verbs, U. Sharipova on active verbs, S. Mukhammedova on action semantic and valency properties of verbs, G. Isakova wrote a monograph on the microfields of action and state. T. Musaev studied semantic verbs in Uzbek language, and M. Otoboeva studied verb graduonymy in detail. From these studies we can learn that language always develops together with society. As a result, the studies also do not end with the solution of one topic or question. There are many topics that are not covered in the above-

mentioned works. In particular, the studies of sound verbs that we started helped to look at the semantics of the verb from a different angle.

It is worth mentioning that the purpose of this paper is to give an interpretation of Uzbek verbs. Accordingly, in general linguistics, the symbolic nature of language consists of two sides: the signifier: the phonetic-sound side, and the signified: the content-semantic side. Which verbs are sound in this regard? First of all, let us analyze the information about the big difference between the concept and the meaning: The perception of an object occurs naturally in the human mind. The image of an object is embodied as a generalization of object symbols. At first, there will be no connection between the sound complex and the object of reality. There is no phenomenon that could be called reflection. At the same time, the question of the presence or absence of motivation between the speaker and the expressed is still the cause of various discussions. In the process of studying verbal lexemes, we notice the connection between sound and image in sound verbs, which facilitates their etymological analysis. For instance, to bark (a-k-k-i-l-l-a-m-o-q) – we pronounce the sound ak-ak, the sound like that b-a-b-a-l-l-a-m-o-q and others. In this case, we found out that the expressive side of the content and the expressive side of the sound are mutually motivated.

In Uzbek linguistics, monographic studies of voiced verbs have not been conducted, but they are reflected in some works published in journals. According to Umida, sound verbs in Uzbek language include words expressing various sound processes as states of action. Sound verbs do not mean a pure action, state, but sound phenomena that manifest themselves in the aspect of action. They are expressed by words and partial exclamations. The article focuses on the diachronic nature of sound verbs (their origin, the possibility of change in time, the loss of the connection between sound and concept, grammatical features).

In our study, we tried to find out that the influence of external factors on the formation of sound verbs is associated not only with the subject. Giving a separate definition of sound and verbal lexemes, when creating the term sound verbs, we paid attention to several areas of science.

It is not a secret that in linguistics, sound is studied in the field of phonetics, it is a unit of speech. Sound is manifested through the acoustic, articulatory properties of phonemes. A verb is a group of words denoting an action, state or event, and each word belonging to this group. What did he do (happen)?, What is he doing (happening)?, What is he doing (happening)? A group of words that is the answer to such questions is called a verb. According to the general grammatical meaning, an independent group of words expressing an action and state is called a verb. Action verbs are verbs denoting actions that occur as a result of the physical activity of people and things. For example, run, move, fall. State verbs are verbs expressing people's internal experiences and the process of transition of things from one state to another. For example, blush, tremble, hesitate. To clarify the concept of sound in detail and clarify the properties of sound verbs, the meaning of sound in physics: sound is a mechanical wave that spreads in the form of vibrations in an elastic medium (air, liquid, solids). Sound is determined by frequency, amplitude and speed, which determines the characteristics of hearing. It also has an explanation in biology: sound is an acoustic signal emitted or received by organisms and serves as a means of communication between biological individuals.

It was found that this process is perceived through the ear and is perceived by the nervous system. As a result, we created a general definition: Voice verbs are verbs that arise in the process of action and state and are formed as a result of "making a sound". Based on the above semantic

groups of verbs, we have included in the table 10 semantic groups of verbs and their brief characteristics, as well as voice verbs:

Table 1-1. Classification of semantic groups of the verb

N.	Semantic groups of verbs	Meaning	Examples
1.	Action verbs	a specific physical action	run, jump, swim, hit, leap, walk.
2.	State verbs	a specific state of something or a person	sleep, laugh, shine.
3.	Verbs of change	indicate a change in the state, form, or quality of a thing or person, these changes include changes in time or processes.	grow, decrease, wither, grow old.
4.	Verbs of origin	the emergence, occurrence, or birth of something or an event.	to appear, to begin, to arise, to be born
5.	Verbs of existence express existence, that is, the presence or absence of something.	These verbs often mean to exist.	to exist, to disappear, to persist
6.	Verbs of acquisition and loss	express actions related to the acquisition or loss of something.	buy, sell, find, lose, take, give away
7.	Verbs of thought and feeling	express internal experiences or mental activity of a person	love, think, feel, fear, learn, understand
8.	Verbs of communication	the process of communication, exchange of information and communication between people	to speak, to tell, to listen, to answer, to ask questions.
9.	Verbs of actions.	related to a change in the state or situation of something. This group includes actions performed on something	replace, repair, restore, destroy, renew
10.	Sound verbs - a result of mechanical vibration of living and	in the process of speech, singing, shouting, crying of people; in the expression of sounds characteristic of animals, insects and birds; these are also verbs denoting a sound audible by	to laugh, to shout, to snort, to thunder, to chat, squeal, to sneeze.

	inanimate objects	any ear, which is produced as a result of natural phenomena, mechanical movement of objects	
--	----------------------	---	--

Definitely, sound verbs are the result of mechanical vibration of animate and inanimate objects: in the process of speech, singing, shouting, crying of people; in the expression of sounds characteristic of animals and birds; as well as speech verbs denoting any audible sound emitted by natural phenomena: To pronounce ak-ak in Uzbek language, which covers a variety of ways in English like bark.

For example, the sound verb to shout: people shout, I hear their steps, the sound verb to shout is a sound process and is mainly included in the series of human sound verbs. But in the poem, the artist created an artistic image that says that the years are shouting. Rustle: I sit - I feel calm, the leaves rustle above my head, given in the meaning to express the rustle of a leaf. For instance, as a grumble: I could not stand it, I burst into tears, Maro grunted. There was a pause. A synonymous version of the verb to cry is used, the artistic tone is enhanced. Moan: again, inspiration made the soul moan, the verb moan is characteristic of man, in the poem it is presented ambiguously. For example, we see this situation in the following lines: listen to my heart at this time "hoy hu" in Uzbek language the echo rumbles like a cannon. The heart hums, in fact, the verb hum is a form of expression of the sound character inherent in natural phenomena (examples are taken from the poetry collection of Osman Nasir).

Brief summary. By summarizing it should be suggested that in the literary form of Uzbek language and dialects, dictionaries and works of art there are about 500 verbs expressing sound. We divided them lexically and semantically into groups of verbs expressing the sounds of living and inanimate objects: people, animals, birds, and created semantic groups of verbs arising as a result of the physical movement of natural phenomena. Such types cover a number of sound verbs, and in the process of analysis we also identified stylistic features.

REFERENCES

1. Rasulov R. 1. Status verbs in the Uzbek language and their obligatory valencies" 1989.
2. Khodjiev A., Verb. Tashkent: Science, 1973.
3. Otaboeva M. Graduonymy of verbs in the Uzbek and English languages. Philological. dissertation, Andijan - 2022.
4. Nurmanov A. Selected works. Volume I. - Tashkent. Academic publication. 2012.